

10:00 - 12:00		Session 1: Introductions
10:00 - 10:15	1a Welcome & Introduction	
10:15 - 10:45	1b Roeland van der Marel (STScI):	The Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope
10:45 - 11:15	1c Jen Lotz (Gemini Obs.):	Overview of Galaxy Formation
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Session 1 live captioning on Monday, 5 October 2020

Russell Ryan: All right. Good morning, everyone out there in TV-land this bright and sunny Monday morning. We're going to wait here another 10 minutes for a few more people to filter in. But we will get started promptly at the stroke of 10:00 Eastern time. We seem to be live on Facebook. Awesome. Thanks, Max. I'm going to start the recording then, too. All right, everyone. We have three more minutes until the stroke of 10:00 by my clock. So just settle in and get comfortable. Get a cup of coffee. We'll get started in just a couple minutes.

All right. By my clock, it's 10:00 a.m. Eastern time. I suppose we should get this train rolling. I want to thank everyone for coming out and joining us for our really exciting Roman conference. This is the conference in a series of many conferences that have been going on as a part of what had been WFIRST. This is the first in that series that is now under the new name, Roman Space Telescope. We have a Code of Conduct which is posted to our slack page. We will be expecting everyone to conduct themselves accordingly. Please, if you have questions, have a quick look at that. We will be using the slack channel to post questions. For attendees and presenters alike, please post your questions for the presenters and the relevant slack channels as they occur to you. It will minimize the downtime at the end of each presenter's talk and I want to remind everyone that we have live captioned streaming. So we have a transcriptionist that will be recording all of this information. And you can go to that link that I just put in the chat to see the live captioning text coming through. And then, finally, when you are a presenter or a chair, please make sure to login as I presenters so that you will have enhanced privileges over the attendees. So with that, I want to get us started. Our first speaker this morning will be Ken. He's the director of STScI. I'm sure most of you know him. So, the floor is yours.

Ken Sembach: Thanks, Russell. Yeah, great to be here this morning with everybody. It's going to be a really interesting conference. And as Russell was saying, it is nice to be able to hold a conference now or a telescope named after Nancy Grace Roman. That is a wonderful thing. I'm going to just pop up a slide real quick on my screen here. If I can do that. For those of you who may not know who Nancy Grace Roman was, I wanted to give you a quick one slide summary of some of her highlights of her career and accomplishments. She was an amazing, amazing woman. A very accomplished astronomer. Absolutely dedicated and consummate public servant. Someone who

really persisted in the face of a lot of obstacles in her career path. She was the first woman on the astronomy faculty of the University of Chicago, but left the University eventually because she realized that she wasn't going to be promoted there. She went to work for NASA. She was the first chief of astronomy and solar task of the first woman to hold an executive position at NASA. She really was the person probably more than anyone who is responsible for shepherding NASA's great observatories right behind the original Orbiting Astronomical Observatories in the late '60s and '70s right through the Hubble course. The field of astronomy today would not be the same had it not been for Nancy Grace's persistence or love of science or absolute commitment to making sure that others could explore the universe and love science the way that she did. Beyond that, she was just a tremendous woman who is a joy to talk to. Someone who was a real champion for women and children. She volunteered for reading for the blind and dyslexic. She was an active member of her church. When I gave a statement at her memorial service at her church, I was honored to do that. And I was astounded by the love that that congregation had for her and the interest they had in her life. And so they were extremely pleased to hear that NASA decided to rename WFIRST after Nancy Grace. I think she would've also been very proud to have had the telescope named after her. I think she would've thought it was a very fitting way to cap her tremendous career. It's up to all of us now to make sure that we help that observatory live up to the legacy of her name and what she has done for us. So let's make sure that we do that.

What are the things that we can do as part of a community is to come together and think broadly and deeply about the kinds of science that are in the realm of possibility with the Roman space telescope. She would've encouraged us to think broadly. I'm encouraging you to do the same today. Don't be bound by the past or deterred by obstacles in your past. Nancy Grace certainly wasn't. And neither should we be. We have a full program here in this particular conference. It's great to see so many people participating. I think Russell was telling me the other day, we had something like 300 people registered for this. I wish all of you a good virtual conference here. Obviously, we would've liked to have done this in person. And there will again be a time when we can do that and help advance the science case for this tremendous observatory. For this week, we will do it virtually, which is the next best thing. I encourage all of you, participate on that slack channel. Ask questions. I will be popping in and out during the conference. And was certain to be answering any questions you might have of me. In the meantime, I'm gonna turn it back over to Russell. I know he's got a few more introductory things that we need to get to before our first talks. I look forward to hearing those and wish you all a good conference.

Russell: Great, thank you so much. Thank you for the nice words about Nancy Grace. She really was a pioneer and instrumental for the space astronomy that we all are attracted to hear. And so, Max has posted on the chat that tomorrow, 3:00 p.m. eastern time, there will be a public lecture about Nancy Grace Roman that will be live streamed on our YouTube channel. So if you don't have access to that or don't know what the URL is, please contact the LOC on the slack channel. Again, related to that, please ask all of your questions as they come to you whether sort of programmatic and technical questions of the lock or scientific questions.

So running about 5 minutes ahead of schedule here. So we will turn it over to Roeland, our next speaker here in just one second. Let's make sure that we don't have any questions or can. Okay, I'm not seeing any questions. We will get started in one second. As we've had a number of new people join, I will just repeat my opening remarks that remember, we have a code of conduct which is posted to our slack page. If you have questions, have a look there. We will be expecting everyone to act accordingly. I have said this twice, but please remember to post all of your questions to the various slack channels. We have different channels for each session and poster and present. Please put your questions there as they occur to you so that at the end of an individual's talk, we can immediately jump right into questions and not waiting for people to type things in. We have live captioning. The link has been posted now and the chat window of BlueJeans Events. Please, if you want to utilize the live captioning, have a look there. I wanted to remind people to log in as a presenter if they will be giving a talk or sharing one of the sessions. With that, we will move on to Roeland, just a couple of minutes early. Our next talk will be by Roeland van der Marel who is the head of Roman science operations here at the Space Telescope Science Institute. Roeland, the floor is yours.

Roeland van de Marel: All right, everyone. I would like to give you a brief overview of the Nancy Grace Roman space telescope before we go into a lot of talks about science and hopefully about some related to scientific uses of this telescope. I work here at Space Telescope Science Institute. We host the science operations center for this

telescope. My role here is to the network package. So to begin with, as you probably know, here in the United States, we use the process of decade-old surveys every ten years where astronomers set the priority for the next decade for large projects and missions both in space and on the ground. A large space recommendations that have come out of this process over the last 50 years are missions that all of you are undoubtedly very familiar with. There has been Hubble, Spitzer, Sophia, James Webb which is due to launch next year. In the 2010 decadal, the committee recommended that construction and launch of a facility that at the time was called WFIRST, the wide-field infrared survey telescope. This has been renamed the Nancy Grace Roman telescope. It is set to launch in the mid-2020s. So, what is the Nancy Grace Roman space telescope? It's a 2.4-meter primary telescope. In the mirror already exists because it was donated by another agency. It was built to look at the earth essentially for spy satellite purposes but was then not used in the end, donated to NASA. NASA has been repressing it for use on this astronomical periscope. It has the same resolution as Hubble, but a key feature of the telescope is it will provide 100 times the field of view of Hubble as well as of Webb. In terms of instrumentation, there is a camera that is the main instrument. It provides imaging as I will talk about. And then, there is a chronograph technology demonstration instrument which is to provide a proof of concept for high contrast light suppression in space with a goal towards future detection with future facilities of earth-like planets. There are various mission partners involved in this mission. It is being led by NASA, obviously. In particular by Gold Art space flight Center but with significant involvement from the Jet Propulsion Laboratory. Also making major contributions to the vital instruments. JPL is providing the iconographic instruments. As science immunity, once the mission launches, those will be the centers that you will likely be primarily interacting with or observation analysis. That there is a range of industry partners as listed at the bottom. Eris has been working on the mirrors for the telescope. Providing a major component for the instrument. And there is also international partners specifically in Europe. See NES in France all contributing things such as ground stations, instrument components and other things. Going to the next slide, this is our version of a slide that can already discussed a much more detail. I will not say much more about it. For those of you have joined a little later, let me just give you my points. This telescope was named after Nancy Grace Roman. She was a leader within NASA appeared in the first of astronomy and solar physics at NASA. The first woman to hold executive position at NASA. She was instrumental in establishing the entire area of instrumentation and research that we are all benefiting from. She was an outstanding scientist, the first woman on the astronomy faculty in the University of Chicago and the recipient of numerous scientific awards. A well-known champion of women in astronomy. An advocate for STEM education in general. Many astronomers have telescopes named after them, what may be a bigger honor is that Nancy even has her own Lego miniature figure. Something that not many astronomers can say. Now, one thing to make very clear at the outset is that you may have heard of beacon in the first or now Roman and thought about this as, you know, a national plan under discussion, something that will happen in the future. This is something I would like to immediately correct. Roman is happening right now. There has been an enormous amount of programming and of the limits already. It just to make it a little clearer, more than a billion dollars has already been spent on this mission. This is in full swing. The primary mirror has been completed recently. A need to be refigured from its original prescription to be used on this telescope. Light detectors are being delivered and tested. The construction of other hardware is well underway with some more examples shown in the images here. How does Roman compared to some of the other great observatories that you might be familiar with in particular in the same wavelength regimes, there is Webb and Hubble. Roman has a similar mirror size as Hubble. A ghost of similar depth. Webb goes much deeper. 11 also goes much further into the infrared specifically into the mid-infrared. Hubble on the other hand goes much further into the ultraviolet. Now, both Webb and Hubble provide a much larger suite of instruments with many different instrument modes that are uniquely suited to follow-up individual targets where things like that. What Roman offers is really the capability. Because his field of view is 100 times bigger than other of the it's unique for different things. First of all, doing accurate statistics on scientific issues where you rely on counting a large number of objects in a large field. As well as finding very dense. Anything that requires things that are rare be it microlensing events, supernova or other things. Of course, the bigger area you cover, the more likely you are to find these things. Now, Roman will they complement each other missions in space. Specifically, there's a number of other projects that will come online in the next ten years and all work -- will work very well together with Roman. As I mentioned, Webb has a unique suite of capabilities and goes very deep. Any unusual objects found with Roman, it would be fantastic to follow-up with Webb and learn much more about them. There is also Ruben. Ruben is also a survey telescope. It covers much more of this sky. We're a very fine resolution that will not be matched by Roman. It does so with ground-based seating and resolution. Similar to Roman, there is a mission and is led by the Europeans the way that NASA contributes. It's also a survey mission. It significantly more focused on Roman on a specific scientific purpose. It is otherwise complementary. More focused on the optical. Roman is more focused on the near infrared. Also provided a small mirror size so it does not go quite

as deep but will likely cover a larger area. So Roman will enhance the power of other missions and projects that will come online in the coming decades. Together, this future suite of instruments will provide unique capabilities in a wide range of areas. What are the instrument capabilities that Roman will offer? There is as you see in the top, there is imaging. There is a suite of seven filters. I will say more about them in the next slide. They covered the wavelength regime from half a microns to 2 microns. When our exposure that will region AB magnitude. There is also split spectroscopic capabilities. The Grissom has higher resolution and does not go quite as deep. It goes to 20.5 an hour. All of these modes cover a field-of-view of about a quarter. On the bottom, there is also the chronograph. This is a science conference topic on evolution. The graph is focused on XL planet science. I will say much more about it in this particular topic which is very briefly, it works in the optical. It covers the wavelength. The goal, the hope is to achieve a magnitude of ten to the minus nine. As mentioned, it will be very interesting for both extra planet science and the greatest amount of stars. There is this whole separate science case in many investigations on this very exciting instrument that I will not have time to talk about here today. In terms of the filters on the wide build instruments, there are seven filters all Widefield filters. The mirror does not offer a narrow line filters on Hubble or Webb or other specialized modes. The prism and the Grism are also shown here. The Grism is a little bit more focused on the infrared. 1 to 2 microns. I mentioned the field of and to really bring home the power that the field-of-view provides, let me show you this slide which is due to a speaker later in this meeting. What is shown here is on a background of the full moon. A number of very well-known surveys with Hubble and other observatories focused on distant galaxies, and other things. Goods, the ultra-deep fields, Cosmos, frontier fields, candles are all shown here. And these have taken an enormous investment of resources with the Hubble telescope you know, think year or years, not just days or months. Now, overlaid here, I show you now that field-of-view over the instrument of Roman. There will be 18 detectors, 4K by 4K. The infrared detectors, but there is more of them, 18 instead of eight. They are instead of 2K. Very similar types of detectors. What you see here is with a single pointing of Roman, you can cover the same area as all of these surveys combined give or take. Now, the power of Roman isn't just that it field-of-view, it is also that it's extremely efficient. It's designed to have very slow and subtle. The observatory will be at the garage point. There will be no earth -- no South Atlantic anomaly to deal with. It means that it is a very efficient telescope. To be able to actually do surveys like the ones that I've done on the Hubble, the factor of improvement you get isn't just the area of the field-of-view, but it's actually much, much bigger. If you do the calculations, what you find is that something like the PHAT survey that was done with Hubble can be done 15 hundredths times faster with Roman. Something like the CANDELS survey can be done a thousand times faster. Something like the 3D ST survey can be done 700 times faster. All of these indicates the tremendous power the observatory will provide for studies with galaxy information and evolution. I have told you about the telescope that is being designed and built. Let me get into it and to what I was and built this way. The decade survey and 2010 at a number of science drivers in mind for this telescope. Specifically, dark energy, XL planets and general acts of physics. To constrain the nature of dark energy and the fate of the universe, to determine the full distribution of planets around other stars, to enable Widefield infrared surveys of the universe to address a wide range of problems. And of course on the bottom right, there's also the technology developments for exploration and new worlds. As well as one of the priorities for the Decadal survey to be a separate item but later adds it to the Roman mission. In terms of the dark energy, there's really several different cosmology methods and themes he appeared at the first is to measure galaxy shapes so as to enable studies that we cleansing. The second is to determine galaxy positions in three dimensions. In particular through wavelength with the Grism. And finally, to the tech type one, supernova and use those as standard candles. These methods will constrain the growth of which are in the universe to expand the history of the universe. And through this will provide constraints on the nature of dark energy, the nature of dark matter, and the amount of those items, as well as any constraints on modified versions of gravity. In terms of XL planet science, science driver enable determination of the mass distribution of planets in the inhabitable zone using microlensing. By designing a telescope that is going to observe multiple fields in the galactic bulge, monitor millions of stars on a rapid cadence and identify an any given time the stars that are in the process of undergoing a microlensing event. Modeling the life cursory events in great detail, it is possible to constrain the presence of planets around the lensing stars. Thus as it is shown in the top right, the distribution of planet masses in part of parameter space that is complementary what is being addressed by Kepler and also tests. Kepler has been doing transit studies. Of those are particularly sensitive to planets that are close into their host star. By contrast, microlensing is much more sensitive to planets at larger distances. Therefore, it will cover a complementary part of the perimeter space so as to enable full senses. Now, third, the telescope is envisioned to enable studies of a wide range of subject areas. This is just a sampling that is shown here on this particular slide. Things such as the evolution and formation of galaxies are the topic of this week's conference. There is many other things for which this telescope provides unique capabilities. Things such as

precision astronomy, solar system science, detection of counterweight counterparts. The same methods that allow measuring out light curves for microlensing also allow studies of astral seismology. And of course, standing in infrared in the Milky Way and other nearby galaxies allow studies of stellar nurseries and clusters as well as the stellar populations in the main bodies and halos over wide range of nearby galaxies to perform galactic archaeology and constrain evolution history of galaxies by resolved populations in the nearby universe. If you search on archive, you will find the wide range of wide papers that have already been written on the number of these topics. There is a white paper on astrology science enabled by Roman that was authored by Roman Sanderson. There's a white paper on solar system science that is late authored by Brian. There's more than four dozen white papers submitted to the ongoing 2020 decadal survey that deal with a wide range of science topics to which Roman will make unique contributions. Now, another thing to point out here is because the telescope is being designed to enable scientific studies and area that require very control of the systematics, the telescope is being designed to facilitate and enable very high quality collaborations. So for BAO measurements, it's necessary to determine wavelength to .1% accuracy. .05% for microlensing, it is necessary to have the automatic stability of over 1%. And for supernova science, it's necessary to have an 0.5% absolute calibration of colors. Now, these numbers may not mean very much to any of you. But just for comparison, these numbers are up to the factor of 10 better than what has been achieved on the Hubble space telescope after 30 years of observation in many, many calibration efforts. What this means is that this telescope will not only provide great data, and will also provide very well calibrated data. That will again enable a whole host of new and exciting science and other areas in addition to dark energy and XL planets that drive some of these calibrations. What is the observational program that will tackle these scientific questions? The goal is to perform Widefield surveys of the universe. Large core community surveys are legacy surveys and smaller focus surveys. One key here is that all the data will be public immediately. Unlike Hubble and Webb, there will be no proprietary periods for the data. All data is taken in the event of how it was proposed, approved, it will be data public immediately. The core community surveys are such that each has a core set of goals. It will be optimized to enable and address the scientific scope. The survey designs remain to be decided through community process that will be set up. The goal of that process is to maximize the science return while addressing some of the core science goals. Currently there are three such surveys. Enable the we cleansing and acoustical investigations. A high latitude time survey to enable the supernova science. In the cosmology investigations associated with it. Galactic bulge time survey to enable the microlensing investigation. In addition to these core community surveys, there will be smaller focus surveys that will be selected through peer review. About a quarter of the mission is set aside for that. That prime mission phase is five years. That is what the mission is constructed and billed for. If the mission is successful, and extended mission phase will undoubtedly be considered. If approved, and extended mission phase will have a much larger fraction of observations. In addition to all of this, there will be archival investigations. Those will be of a variety of scope. They will be there with the analysis that the survey data will obtain. There will be larger key project type investigations to address the major science goals of the mission such as the dark energy parameter or the XL planet distribution or maybe other things. There will also be a smaller archival project we can do that kind of archival science that is currently approved on other great observatories to facilitate a wide range of scientific studies. An important thing to point out is all the opportunities for science, funding, and a moment remain to be fully decided. This is a wide open mission. You are all invited to contribute, propose, analyze, and all of the other things that are involved in making a mission a success. Now, while I said that everything is still open in many ways, certainly an enormous amount of effort has been spent to think about what these core surveys could be like. In particular to drive the design and requirements for the mission that is currently being built. This is just an example slide up with the high latitude imaging could look like and similar slides like this exists. The goal is not to go into this in any detail about to show you that the science investigation teams that have been selected a number of years ago and that will be disbanded next year -- so toward the design phase have done a lot of thinking and thought about, where could fields be located? What filters -- what would the exposure times be? although things have been thought through. Concepts exist. Any major questions remain to be decided. Are we going to cover a narrower area deeper or a wider area more shallow, our top level questions that still remain to be decided. All of this is more to indicate that four people who are interested, there's a lot of things to look into and build upon. But really, the complete fine tuning and design remains to be decided. You have 3 minutes remaining. Yep. There's other great science that can be done such as the Roman deep field would be a very exciting thing to do. Roman offers the opportunity to get ultra deep field like death over 100 times the area. This would provide an increase survey volume and would overcome any current limitations that exist regarding two number counts that limit what we can do for example with luminosity functions, extrapolation of rare objects and things like that. With a deep field, there might be hundreds of galaxies in the range of 9 to 10. We will talk about this more later. There's a number of white papers listed at the bottom that you can go look at if I thought about

this in some detail already. Either way, it is such a deep field to become a reality which is not been decided, it will require coordination within the community as well as with other projects to arrive at optimum strategies. Now, one of the things about the Roman surveys is they will be among the most information rich data sets ever collected. This slide shows lots sensitivity versus grass for a number of surveys you may be familiar with. The arrows here show where the example concept for high latitude imaging survey would lie in this diagram. It's clear that they very much lie on the top right. Together with your surveys of the coming decade. This clearly illustrates the information content and the science that is going to be enabled by all of these surveys is going to be fantastic. Now, to explore the science that Roman will in neighbor, it's important to simulate what the data will look like. The community has developed a number of packages to study for example what galaxy fields or spectrum may look like. Here we have been developing a number of simulators that are publicly available from the listed website. Things that deal with points. Functions, exposure time calculation, simulations of small fields or large fields, field overlay tools, et cetera. There is also a page that is maintained that maintains an inventory of simulations and models by various Roman partners. I encourage all of you to explore these tools. When used, such tools allow construction of a very detailed simulated scenes. What is shown here is how the Roman field of view would overlay on the Andromeda galaxy. And some of blowups provide some detail based on actual simulations extrapolated from what we know from surveys. What this shows is the tremendous amount of detail that will be available in any given Roman pointing. The specific simulation was done by Williams and his group. I'm sure you will talk about it later in the meeting using a tool with the aid of a tool that we have developed here. There is a link at the bottom where people can go to. The key thing here again to point out is that it took 402 pointing's with Hubble and with Roman, the same area will be covered and it will be done much faster as well. So, all of this poses a challenge, because Roman will produce so much data that is different than other NASA missions that we have all been used to. It is the first foray of NASA XL physics. Catalogs were all used -- they are not necessarily huge. One of the things about Roman as opposed -- we expect many people not want to use the catalogs. The individual survey data because of the space-based resolution, the pixel level data will be incredibly rich. Both of catalogs and the pixel level data will provide unique science opportunities. The capabilities required to download the process in a very large data scents will exceed whatever users can do with standard resources. Just to illustrate this within a matter of weeks after the Roman mission starts, the archive size will be the same as the complete archive of Hubble after 30 years. Data products will be generated by multiple mission partners. There will be things such as calibrated and mosaic images, catalogs and other things like that. The most important data products will be staged in the cloud and colocated with computational resources for interaction as I will discuss below. Also, the pipeline we are developing at the Institute here for the imaging modes will be open source and modular, thus enabling custom read processing. If people want to insert additional modules, that should be much easier in this pipeline then other pipelines like on Hubble that you may be familiar with. All of the data products independently retro generated will go into a single archive which will be hosted here at the Institute and the archive for space telescopes. The archive will really be the key for the community to perform Roman science. It is important to point out here that only current great observatories -- most science is already archival. Half of the sciences archival at present. Archival science is incredibly important, also for accessibility and diversity. By providing a well-documented accessible archive, the number of institutions that can publish and perform state-of-the-art science increases by a factor of 2 to 4. There will also be a data management environment for the WFI. That will be a cloud-based science platform for high-level data processing. This enables users to bring software. That is important because the archive for Roman is estimated at the end of the mission to be 4 to 20 petabytes. A download data to your local system and analyze it there is just not going to work when the data for most users -- the environments that is to be provided will include things such as environments and notebooks for ease of access and learning. And sharing of software by science center names in the community. It's possible to build a cool tool and shared with the rest of the community and allow other people to do other science with it. Although this also means that users on this mission will have to get used to interact with data in new ways. The old models will not necessarily work anymore, and people have to get used of interacting with catalogs and pixel level data in a way that is unique to big data surveys and data sets of this nature. So how do you join the Roman conversation? We hope that many of you will do. There's a range of websites shown on the right that we encourage everyone to go to and learn more about the mission about observatories and instruments and science plans opportunities and data simulation tools et cetera. Look for opportunities to influence the court community surveys. The idea that there will be optimized with input from the community and you are all representatives of that community. Also look for proposal opportunities to begin next year for a range of preparatory science programs. As I mentioned, the science investigation teams have been in place for a number of years. Their terms will end next year. As teams may continue to exist. But at that point, new opportunities for involvement and funding will be provided by NASA. Please look out for that. We encourage everyone to propose for opportunities as

relevant. Just to conclude, Roman development is well underway and making great progress. Roman will provide a wealth of breakthrough science opportunities both by itself and in combination with other missions and projects. We hope that you will all get involved. This is an open mission. Most of the program remains to be fully decided. Please think about it and contribute. Finally, I hope you will all enjoy this conference. In particular as you hear about all the great things that are going on in a galaxy formation evolution, think about how the Roman space telescopes can advance your own science. And how you can use them to contribute to the mission program and help make it a success. With that, thank you for attention, and I opened it up for any questions that there may be.

Roland, we have one question. Are there any planned synergies with the surveys? Yes, there's a lot of synergies with the survey. The mission will launch before Roman. There is certainly a fair bit of thought that has gone into particular both the synergy between that and Roman and of course along with three of them, one thing that would be really fantastic that a lot of people have talked about and written white papers on his joint analysis of all that data. For example, if you think about Rubin, it's ground-based resolution. You can use the space-based data to disentangle objects at a higher resolution. Things that may look as one object and Rubin may actually be several objects close together. You will tell that from the space based data. What you really want is you want both in the optical and infrared. You may need to combine missions. Certainly for dark energy, there's been a lot of thought how they will help each other. Is very likely that it will influence other science areas. It is also big improvements to be made. And, you know, really more use cases come up in this meeting. We would like to hear about them. One of the things specifically is that the excess to that is not quite as open to the American community as is the excess to Roman or Rubin data to the community. Within the U.S., there is a consortium of a couple dozen scientists that have been selected by an asset with access to the data. It is not widely available to the whole community. In terms of the politics to make all of these work together and provide some kind of an equal opportunity model, there are still things that need to be discussed and worked out.

Okay. Thank you. Also, there were many more questions that you have time to answer on the slack channel. I encourage you to visit that channel and answer those questions if you can. I will do so. Thank you. Russell, you are muted.

Okay, so let me just turn -- our next speaker is Jennifer Lotz. She will be giving us an overview of the field of galaxy formation. I just want to remind you again that questions can be posted on the slack channel under session 1 in the thread under Jen. We will ask some at the end of her talk. Take it away.

Jennifer Lotz: Okay, all right. So thank you all for inviting me to this fabulous conference. I'm really excited about the prospects of the Roman Space Telescope. I was asked to give an overview of galaxy evolution and prospects for the future. I'm going to apologize now, because that's a really big task to do in 25 minutes I know a number of people who are at this conference have already been thinking very deeply about what Roman space telescope can do for galaxy evolution. I really am looking forward to hearing those talks. I've had the privilege over my career to be involved with a number of Hubble space telescope surveys that have really impacted the way that we see galaxy evolution. And I think are really great Pathfinders for what the Roman space telescope will do. So, you know, what have we learned from HST imaging? Roland gave a really great introduction and described the differences between what Roman will do versus what Hubble will do. With Hubble, we get these fantastically high resolution DIVA multicolor images. And we have learned how to really make the most of these. Thousands or tens of thousands of galaxies from some of these surveys, colors of the precise photometry. We can get very good -- we can infer from their spectral energy distributions, the galaxies at higher redshifts, we can infer with their UV are paired with a high resolution images, we can measure their sizes, their structural properties at resolutions and look for asymmetries that are associated with larger activity. If you combine this hour of Hubble with nature's telescope such as the cluster, you can do even more. So that magnification nature's telescopes brown lenses provide an additional factor of higher spatial resolution resolutions less than a particular parsec. It can also help you probe the properties of intrinsically fainter galaxies that are really difficult to see with Hubble alone. Along with these imaging surveys and with the advent of fairly efficient -- chism capabilities, we now have actually very large surveys. Here, I'm showing from the survey. Again, with thousands or tens of thousands of galaxies, we can look for -- sometimes we can see absorption features of every galaxy in that field. This gives us reasonably good redshifts. And even environments are possible to

measure with the infrared Widefield camera grisms and for a smaller subset of those objects in these surveys, those that are bright or large or things that are samples on the order of hundreds or thousands, you can spatially resolve these features with Hubble. This gives you spatially resolved maps of those revision lines from which you can infer star formation. It you can look at blind ratios to tell you with the dust content is viewed you can look for spatially resolved points that are signatures of active galactic nuclei. So this is a plot from Forrester. Review which was focused on the star formation. This just shows all the surveys that have happened in the last couple of decades that have really helped open up this window into galaxy evolution. I have circled in the blue box here the role that the imaging and surveys have played. This is showing that sample sizes of Gallic sizes versus the spectrum resolution at the surveys -- there are many surveys that Hubble have done that are not on this because they are aimed at a red shift or lower red shift including the Hubble field, good, apples, clearing. Lensing clusters surveys including class, Buffalo. There is just many rich data sets out there that have really opened our eyes in the window of galaxy evolution. The exciting thing about Roman of course is as described is the sample sizes are going to increase by factors of 100. We are really going to open up go front and say hundreds of thousands of galaxies to study, millions of galaxies -- one of the challenges that we had with Hubble of course is that we have to decide where we are designing our surveys whether to go wide or to go deep. And much of the progress that we have made as required us to combine both wide and deep surveys in what is known as a strategy. This is a figure which was put together for planning the Hubble frontier fields in which we have looked at the existing samples available as a function of galaxy magnitudes versus the area covered. You can see that to probe the dynamic range to really understand it galaxy evolution you have to combine quieter surveys that are more shallow with deeper surveys to get both ends of the luminosity function and to probe that full range of the dynamic range and luminosity of galaxies but also redshifts. Initiated region there you can see the benefits of adding the Hubble frontier fields. So I like to sometimes say that the study -- an observational study of galaxy evolution is essentially the study of plotting the properties of galaxies as a functional red shift. The survey paper shows I think the combination of several decades worth of work to show what the average physical properties are. A number of these surveys. You know, we have learned what the star formation rate is, the main sequence of galaxies, study the stellar mass function for all galaxies and redshifts three and beyond, we have a look at how that depends on the star formation history of those galaxies. We have made great progress and understanding the size mass relationship of galaxies. We have connected that galaxies to their essential mass densities in their structures. Even as with Hubble, we are starting to be able to use the spectroscopic capabilities to study the relationships. So, you know, all of this needs to be connected back to our understanding of theoretical models of galaxy revolution and a broadbrush picture has emerged in which we now understand galaxy growth as being connected intimately to its cosmic web. Dark matter halos are forming out of their initial density formation. These galaxies assemble their mass along the cosmic -- in a surprisingly regular and well described way. The star formation within galaxies, we understand to be regulated by gas inflows and outflows. Stellar star formation feedback is particularly important. Active nuclei are important. We also understand that the heating and -- it's an important factor in exchanging evolution of galaxies. With Hubble, we have understood now that the structures of galaxies are also a critical component of understanding galaxy growth. In many ways, galaxy structures are a tracer of -- if I galaxy has had smooth secretion over its lifetime, and tends to build up a lot of gas and creates high momentum and enables the formation of large disk. If I galaxy has had a turbulent history, this leads to angular momentum transfer, the creation of bulges, which is also correlated with the growth of supermassive black holes in their centers. Environment and local density of galaxies is also known to be important particularly at low redshifts. This results in increased merger activity and also the destruction of Lomas galaxies. There are a lot of details that we yet do not know. So some of the things that Hubble has really helped us understand and help us identifies some very early galaxy is that we are able to see with Hubble, galaxies that appear within a few hundred million years of the Big Bang. And we know these are rapidly growing in time. I know that the bulk of the universe of stars formed between redshifts. They know that the global star formation is well behaved. Hubble has informed this in combination with ground-based telescopes. We are able to see that this is linked -- intimately linked to what is available. They are able to see that star formation in galaxies is shutting down over cosmic time. This process is starting. I galaxy quenching is going to its galaxy structure, stellar mass and supermassive black hole. But there's a lot of detail that we don't understand. And I think there are number of questions that Roman is really very Wells needed to tell us about. As was said, understanding those samples, the first rare and massive galaxies and supermassive black holes grow. What drives the invert connections between galaxy assembly, sizes, the growth of their dark matter halos and the scatters of the relationships. What is the role of local environment? So, Roman in many ways is similar to the Hubble space telescope in the wavelength coverage in many of the broad bands that will be available. It's a Grism and prism modes will be spectacularly efficient. The critical thing for galaxy evolution is this factor of hundred and field of view.

This is an old slide borrowed from Jason. He made it before this telescope was named after Nancy Grace and Roman. You can see the dramatic improvement over the Hubble deep Field's can be given in terms of the numbers of galaxies that a single shot with Roman would be able to give you. So, the questions for Roman space telescope really need to leverage the advantage that wide field of view and somewhat improved capabilities we give you. Statistics, we have been starved with statistics even with samples of thousands, there's questions that can't really be answered. And so, with Roman, we will be able to look at the distributions and the properties of galaxies and their intrinsic dispersions. These larger volumes will help us explore both intrinsically rare objects, short-lived phenomena like galaxy mergers or quasars or things that are hard to observe such as systems or alpha emitters that need to be detected. This larger volume in a single shot will help us lower the cosmic variance of the CDMs that we see. The higher resolution Grism furnace will give us better redshifts over a larger field of view. And these high spatial resolution images over large areas will also allow lensing studies which will provide a new probe -- a statistical probe of dark matter. We have not really studied before. So, just to go a little bit further in terms of what would be available for high ratio galaxy studies, one of the limiting factors for the Hubble deep Field -- frontier fields was low-volume for high galaxies. Last year, you see the deal ends volumes for the frontier fields and galaxy clusters. On the right here, you can see that estimates of the fractional cosmic variance as a function of the interesting UV luminosity or high redshifts galaxies. You can see that bright magnitudes for these small fields of view both for Lynn's surveys and for the on Lynn's ultra-deep fields, they were really quite limited the single-point use of Hubble in terms of our interpretation of those bright galaxies samples at high redshifts. While James Webb will certainly probe deeper down the luminosity function, its field of view is only a factor of 2 larger within the wide field. Camera three, infrared field of view. So, even with deep data surveys, our studies will continue to be limited by the intrinsic line of sight variability's due to the density of fluctuations in the universe. Of course, within ultra-deep Roman field, we will get a much larger volume for these galaxies. And be able to go both deep and wide. We won't have to make that trade-off. We won't have to be limited by the strategies associated by combining wide and deep surveys as we have been with Hubble.

Five more minutes. Okay, great, thank you. These surveys of course will pick up the rear, bright and massive galaxies. One of the surprises of this wide field studies that we have been able to do with HST parallel studies is that there are a number of intrinsically bright high redshifts galaxies that they are not well understood. As I said, another challenge we have had is to detect alpha through the IDM at high redshifts. Having wider fields of view, more likely to find lines of sight and make it through would be fantastic and revolutionary for understanding the high redshifts universe. Of course, we will also be able to detect some of the first quasars and get a better handle on the growth of the supermassive black holes. Looking at lower redshifts, one of the things that I'm interested in is understanding galaxy size evolution. This has been one of the key results I think coming out of the candle survey. One of the challenges of course is again trying to understand the statistics and higher massive for rare use. This is one of the aims of the cosmos survey which was trying to survey the cosmos very quickly with the Widefield camera infrared. And was able to increase the numbers of the most massive galaxies, the stellar mass was greater and the survey. One of the things that we want to understand is how and why the sizes of galaxies have seemed tied to their star formation histories. What is the role of central density? Are the sizes of galaxies truly tied to the sizes of their halos? What is the role of mergers and assembling and creating growing this galaxy over time? So, in my last few minutes, I'm going to make a little bit of a pitch now for really trying to make the most of the very large data samples. So much of what observational astronomy has done with these fantastic surveys from Hubble and other facilities as plot the properties of galaxies as a function of redshifts. Look at those distributions and try to understand how they change over time. But the way that we do this is fairly simplified. We will often will fit a line, so that they galaxies samples into red and blue and try to understand if the slope of that line or they intersect on changed. Sometimes, we will make histograms. This is a histogram of a specific star formation range. The medium of that histogram changed to the dispersion of that histogram changed. How do we connect that back to models? We can make a fit of function to histograms. In the case of stellar mass functions, the sector functions, we look to see if the fitting parameters changed. So these approaches are somewhat limited in the fact that they really make simplified assumptions about galaxy distributions. The parameterized simple models often end up spending the data. Sometimes this is good because you're able to tell a pretty simple story with a straight line. In truth, we are throwing away a lot of information. I would argue that we can really try to do better in the era of big data. The technique that I have been quite interested in playing around with is looking at something called extreme deconvolution. So, my inspiration for this was a study done by Lauren Anderson where she used Gaia and millions of stars. Through this technique was able to essentially take what is a fairly noisy distribution of stellar magnitude diagram, but with very well understood errors and very large samples and essentially a pullout from this a lot of the features that are well known and well studied from the stellar magnitude diagram such as the red Giant branch and red clump and so forth. There is no reason why we can't

do something similar with galaxies, particularly as we get samples that we are talking about with the Roman space telescope. So with a fairly noisy sample and a well understood error for thing like this, past relationship, begin to deeply resolve these errors and fit this with not a single line, but with a set of mixture models. But this gives you in the end is an empirical description of the size mass distribution. As we do and galaxy evolution, we can take a look at how this evolves with redshifts. Not only do you get an intrinsic distribution as a function of redshifts, but now you essentially have a model, of how galaxies evolved in size and mass or any two or any set of parameters that you choose is a function of time. You can use this to create the likelihood at the galaxies are appearing or disappearing with time relative to that model. If you take the model created here from the observed distribution of sizes and masses in high redshifts, you compare that to the model created from this mixed year model at a lower redshifts, you can compute the difference for a set of data of it being drawn from the higher redshifts model from the lower redshifts model and determine whether galaxies at a given size are mass are appearing with time or disappearing. So when we do this with the sizes and masses derived from galaxies in the candles survey combined with the galaxies from another survey, very quickly see that the largest galaxies appear to be appearing most rapidly with time in redshifts three. This is that Delta likelihood as a function of size. This really interesting that of correlations of how galaxies appear and disappear with time. You can see for the lower redshifts, there is something 10,000 galaxies in the lower redshifts sample. You get a really robust description of what is happening in that. If you compared to the low to six derived from the highest, it can be quite challenging to figure out what is going on there. So, by using more powerful statistics, but also by using the large samples, it can really make great progress, I think. This is the same thing. Looking how the likelihood compares to stellar mass, with star galaxies appearing most rapidly with time, galaxies with ten and ten to the five are the galaxies that grow the most. Just to summarize, the last 30 years with the Hubble space telescope has really transformed our understanding of galaxy evolution. Not only that, and has taught us some very valuable strategies we are developing surveys. The Roman space telescope is going to provide an incredibly efficient survey mission. Give us numbers of galaxies more than 100 times what we are able to do currently. That means that we are no longer going to have to choose between wide and deep surveys or try to cobble together a very different surveys with very different approaches. The telescope is going to open windows on those very rare options, objects that are short lived and objects that are just intrinsically hard to see. These better statistics are not only going to give us more objects, but give us a better understanding of what the intrinsic distribution of galaxy properties. I would argue with these better statistics, we should not only just count more galaxies, but we should make use of that to develop more sophisticated approaches, more data analysis, more sophisticated approaches to how we compare that. All right, thanks very much.

Thank you, Jen. I should have said earlier, no applause, but you can't hear it from people. Imagine they are all applauding. That is the downside of these virtual events. On the upside, there's an interesting question here. Star formation properties together with star formation fuel for example since it is not yet a survey instrument, wet synergies with Roman surveys do you envision to look at the coal gas and star together? I should point out that the beginning part of this press all my question has to do with understanding galaxy evolution and the importance of looking at the nebular lines to do so.

Yeah, I think both even with James Webb, we've got this trade-off between big fields of view and things with relatively smaller -- with a survey instrument, you are going to find those interesting objects. You're going to find the things that you think are the most worthwhile for study. You will be able to construct samples of either of the things based on their admission lines are based on what you infer as their masses of the things most worthwhile for study. Will also be able to construct samples saying you want to observed 50 galaxies and you wanted to span a wide range of stellar masses. Roman will provide the samples for the follow-up. Another is flying at the same time. Even with ground-based telescopes such as Gemini.

Okay. One last question. Great talk. I should have said probably who the questions are from. Anyway, this is from Rachel. I like the approach. Have you tried applying it to predictions from cosmological models and simulations?

I have not. That is only because I have not had much time in the last few years to work on this. She knows that I have been thinking about it for a while. But I think that is an excellent approach. I think both for taking the cosmological models are they are, something like energy being what those distributions that you get out of the model look like and how they do in a side-by-side comparison. You can also directly take a sample of galaxies and red shift 2 from your observations and do this likelihood to see where the true multidimensional differences between the model and the

observed galaxy distributions are. I think that will tell you not Jos, your line didn't quite fit or the dispersion is different and really pinpoint those galaxies that are the true outliers and are the best tests for your theoretical model.

Okay. Thanks. There are more questions on the slack channel for you. I encourage you to visit that channel. It would be under your name, that thread under your name and answer some more of the questions. Otherwise, we have time for our next speaker. And thank you, once again for a wonderful talk.

And, our next presenter is Dara Norman who will be talking about advancing inclusion through access. And she is at the National Optical Infrared Astronomical Research Laboratory.

Dara Norman: Thank you for inviting me. I'm going to talk about advancing inclusion through access. I think Roman is a great opportunity to discuss this. I do want to point out the fact that I am at NOIRLab which is the nickname for a new observatory. And all of the opinions that I express my talk are entirely my own and not necessarily those of NOIRLab. So I'm going to start with the Decadal survey. I'm starting with this because the decadal over the years has really been an agent of culture change in our field. And even though we don't think of that now, it has been in the past. And I think that especially with both Roman and with Rubin, we are looking at opportunities for real culture change in how we do science. So I'm gonna start by explaining this idea of culture change through the decadal surveys by showing you a page out of the first decadal survey in 1964. It is important to point out that there have only actually been six decadal surveys. This first basic survey was about the astral professional workforce and its development and how to modify workforce demographics. You can see here, one of the titles of the chapters was the dilemma of astronomy graduates in 1964 with another title as manpower which we might say workforce these days. The main point, the main point of the survey really was that people were concerned that there were not enough public telescopes and instruments available for folks to do good theses. And so from that recognition of an issue came the opportunities to build the national optical observatory and national radio observatory for public astronomy community use. So when people tell you that the decade-old surveys are only about science, they are forgetting the fact that you need a workforce that actually is going to do the science. Even the first basic survey was really about the state of the profession. And providing the tools to do this science. So, of course, the Roman and the Rubin observatories were endorsed by the decadal surveys. They represent an opportunity again for cultural change in astronomy and astrophysics, for opportunities to reiterate our values, our norms, and our traditions for how we do science, and how we are going to do science over the next decade. And here is a nice picture of the women in astronomy meeting back in 2009. So in our field, we have already been embarking on this idea of cultural change through the informal institutional change. The idea that different groups of individuals and collaborations have been looking at how we do our science and how we include as many folks as possible in the participation of doing that science. We have been looking at how we put together the opportunities, how we distribute the resources, how we communicate, how we are able to communicate within large collaborations, having codes of conduct, having an actual committees that look into how well any of our collaborations are doing on inclusion. And also talks again at science meetings that engage the idea of our workforce and how we are doing our science, not just what science we are doing. However, if we really want to embrace a cultural change, we can have to move into areas of more formal institutional change. And some of those areas of change I've listed here, we presented at Obama's president council of advisors on science and technology back in 2016. And the sun is up, the first one is really about access. Access both to opportunities to give -- to give advice on how science should be done and opportunities also to worry about what resources are going to be available. We need to worry about policies and whether we are addressing the right problems and concerns. We need to worry about broadening participation. Broadening participation in the sense that we are actually broadening our workforce and our research participation. And not only looking at public outreach and education. Finally, we are going to need our leaders to really be pushing on these ideas that we need resources for these kinds of inclusion activities that they really need to be engaged for us to get the best science. So I'm going to start with access. Access is absolutely crucial to inclusion. First, I'm gonna talk about advisory access. That is the access of people to be able to give input into how to make resources available. The second thing I'm going to talk about is actually scientific resource access. That is actually making people able to do that science through access to data. I wrote an article back in 2018 -- I don't have a lot of time here that expresses these ideas more fully about big data and whether it can be a catalyst for inclusion. So, first talking about advisory access. You know, we pick our advisory committees, and we ask for advice looking at a number of different kinds of expertise. And we are looking at these expertise at these

areas of expertise, we also need to look at people's personal experience science. That informs really how you understand things about how easy it is to get the data, how many barriers there are to getting data, and how many resources you actually have access to. I have a quote here from a transgender woman who said and heard TED Talk, I didn't know what I didn't know. The idea here is that as a man, he was very in tune to the fact that there were differences between genders. There might have been unequal treatment for women. It wasn't until she actually became a woman that she really experienced all of the nuance and all of the ways in which women were discriminated against in the world. Likewise, I think that while we might intellectually understand what some other folks in the field are experiencing, we don't really know exactly what they are experiencing. We need them to be able to tell us. We need folks like this from all of these different backgrounds on our committee is us their expertise about how we need to make resources available and ways in which we can make science more inclusive. So when we build our -- when we build our committees and we build our panels, we want to be very inclusive about all of these areas of expertise. One more thing I think that we don't do is often, we hold up our folks on the committee's as you are the expert in this. We want your opinion. We don't often reiterate that they are one person of a few people. We would actually like them to explore their networks, talk to people that they know, get information to bring back to these committees. In that way, we can actually expand out opportunities to gather expertise together insight without having to have committees that have 50 or 60 people on them. In the first talk, there were discussions of how putting together how ribbon science is going to get out to the public. Those are still to be decided and still in flux and still happening. And so, right now, there is the Roman science interest group that has been recently put together and will have its first meeting this week. It's going to look at their broad-based community input to how Rubin science or Rubin data will get done or get put out or people to do their science and the interests of the scientific community and how Rubin -- sorry, I'll Roman will serve those interests. And so, when I looked at the list of institutional affiliations of people who are now on that committee, what I noticed is that they were lacking in some of the people who can be there who can give us their expertise on doing science at smaller institutions who will be able to help us understand these biases. I have this little asterisk in there because that person is me. I plan to spend whatever time I'm on this committee really trying to reiterate that we need expertise from a very broad area of the community if we are really going to make data more inclusive to the broad community. And why do we need to do that? People don't know what they don't know. Back in 2012, I wrote a white paper for the national academies for a few colleagues. They identified nine barriers that people of color face in astronomy and astrophysics. You might notice these barriers extend to many different kinds of folks in the community. Women of color obviously sit at a special intersection of concerns about gender as well as concerns about race and ethnicity. And so, these top 2 barriers are the ways in which I think access to data might be able to help mitigate some of these barriers. These are difficulties in building that works and collaboration. If you're able to get to data easily and it helps you with building networks and collaborations. The second is that women of color have difficulty achieving insider status in the fields. I insider status, what I'm really talking about are those little things that you get asked to do in order to be considered a full member of the community. Those are things like giving talks, being asked to review papers, being asked to join collaborations. To bring those home about how data might be able to mitigate some of those barriers, I want to show you this top graph which shows the number of papers per year published from Hubble data. You can see here that in the blue, the blue area shows the number of published papers from people who got time directly on the telescopes. And the orange area is people who published data basically from the archives, from all archival data. You can see that over time, the number of papers coming out from the archives actually is equal to -- and then, it looks like it might even be starting to overtake the number of papers that come out from people who directly got time. Josh Peake looked into who are writing these archival papers. In the plots below, you can see that he has plotted for folks at larger institutions, the number of publications over time for folks who are using both archival data and directed data. There is a color switch here. The archival data is in blue. For folks that large institutions, those numbers track each other very well. There's not a lot of different. For people at smaller and other institutions, you can see there's a big difference in the number of people for the number of publications that are able to get out from the archives verses from direct data. And the question is, can are we promoting insider status in effect moving people from being able to do their science from archival data to being able to actually get time on the telescopes. So, it is possible that really having data available so folks can help move us in the direction of better inclusion. But archives are not enough. I was really happy to hear on the first talk that there will not just be archives for Rubin. The reason archives are not enough is because, you know, we talk about diversity, equity, and inclusion. But equity and equality are not the same thing. It has taken me a while to really come to even using the word equity, because I didn't really quite understand it in the context of our academic lives in science. What I realize is that equality is a state of being equal. If we take all of that data and throw it over the wall and say it's all available. Anybody can have it, go ahead and do it. That is not the same as actually the state of

equity, which is really concerned about outcomes, about the quality of being fair. About the quality of supporting people to reach their goals. If you don't have the same resources as someone else, the quality is not doing you much good. Equity is what is going to do you the most good. It's focused on the outcomes of what you are able to achieve, because you have access to that data. An access to resources to actually use that data. So in order to promote equity for data sets, we don't just need archives, we also need things like science platforms and tools that enable people to use these very large data sets and to be able to make sense of them without having their own resources at their institutions directly available. This is just a plug for our communities science and data center which is put together the tools like a broker for filtering transient data. And the data lab which was a science platform with Jupiter notebooks and catalogs available through these platforms in order to help people do their science. The other thing that we have to worry about our policies. We put together policies for reasons. But what we don't do is we don't often go back and look at those policies and look at where they have gone well or they haven't gone so well and worry about where they might need to be tweaked. The two policies I'm citing here are open skies. Open skies is the idea that Publix telescope facilities are equally open to everyone. That is regardless of whether they actually have access to private facilities are not. This is a great thing to do, right? Anybody with a good idea that has scientific merit can come and propose to any telescope. On the other hand, they should actually think about the fairness of people who don't have any kind of access to telescopes versus people who have access to other telescopes. Who has the advantage in these unequal situations? To mitigate sort of some of the bad things about open skies, we need to focus on the implementation. You need to focus on a regular assessment and revision of our policies on open skies. The same with dual anonymous. Dual anonymous, the idea that both the proposer and the reviewer are unaware of each other that you don't have names on proposals, that is great. You can focus on the science of the proposal better. On the other hand, it can conflict again with other science mission priorities. People who are at institutions that maybe don't have access who might want to -- you might not have the privileges of being able to put together this same kind of proposal that other folks can as those with private data. Sorry to interrupt. Five more minutes. I meant to tell you to tell me that. We want to look at and review our policies. And as we review these policies, we want to be aware that research inclusion is very important. And we should be valuing it as part of how we assess the scientific merit of our proposals. Some areas of research inclusion that are important are again, this idea of policies and procedures to support mutually beneficial partnerships. The idea of being able to help people to network and collaborate, the opportunities for people to have infrastructure that allows them to really get not just have data available, but actually use that data to support their science. Finally, opportunities to train on those tools, on those platforms for people to be more effective in doing their science. When I say training, I don't just mean for graduate students. I'm talking about for all levels of folks who might want the training. So, we need our leaders to be leaders. We need them to really step up to the challenge of talking about these issues of inclusion in science and what that means. What it means for some of our policies. There are a lot of good ideas that people have put together and written about. You can find some of them in these references I this year. If we are really going to change the culture, make a culture that's more inclusive in science, we really need to start having our leaders talk about these issues and look at ways to fund and provide resources for the broader community. And so, this is my summary slide. We have to be really deliberate and how we embrace the practice embrace and practice diversity equity and inclusion in order to advance cultural change in astronomy and astrophysics. This starts with access. Access is crucial. Advisory access and data access -- we need to make sure that we are looking at our policies, and we are reviewing them and making sure that they are actually doing inclusive work that we want them to be doing. Finally, we wouldn't need to embrace research inclusion as a valued part of our scientific merit I think that will be the best legacy for both Nancy Roman and Rubin. Thanks, I will take questions now.

Thank you, Dara. We hear the applause internally even though we don't hear them on the screen and in the conference. There are many interesting questions. I'm going to start with one. "Other petabyte scaled projects planned for this decade, data access and will be largely or entirely at the data hosting sites." Jupiter notebooks and other resources. Is this access analysis framework going to help improve access to everyone? What more should be planned in these frameworks that can make them more effective for smaller institutions?

I definitely think it is a big step forward that you will be able to do your analysis on platforms where the data are. I have the experience of having done a sabbatical at Howard University where, you know, I didn't know what I didn't know until I went to a place with fewer resources. Then I found out that in fact it was really important to be able to say, use the data lab over a connection and reduced data or and analyzed data. So those kinds of science platforms are going to be crucial to helping folks at small schools. What else do we need? I'm at an observatory. I'm at a

national lab. I don't know. We need to engage that people who do know and ask them, what are the things that they need? The items that I listed on that research inclusion slide, those are things that small and underserved institutions told me would be beneficial for them. We need to put those people on our committees and asked them, what do you need to do science with these telescopes?

Okay, I'm gonna ask you two questions together because they go together. These are a combination of questions. How do you see the most important steps to motivate the inclusions of researchers at smaller institutions? For smaller and larger institutions, there's a difference in the archive versus research in how much of the archive data work was funded. Apologies to the questionnaires if I mangled their questions.

That's okay, I think I got the point. I expect that resources to fund archival research are key, absolutely key. Again, this is where I think asking folks at small institutions, what are the barriers? What is keeping you from being able to use archives? This is another reason we need to ask those folks and talk to those folks to find out what they need and what they want to do. I expect that being able to fund a student or bond your time in the summer, right? Are going to be key to being able to participate in that research. How do we get those folks who participate? Well, we actually have to recruit them. We have to let them know their resources. We have to let them know that they are welcome. I think a lot of people at smaller institutions might just say, I can't compete. I have a lot of things to do. And if there is no way for me to break in, and I have other things to do. We need to make our partnerships and collaborations mutually beneficial to the folks at smaller institutions as well as then participating with folks at larger institutions. We need to have folks at larger institutions understand the benefits of working with folks at smaller institutions. The benefits of having students who are able to get that really close training with their advisors. And then Emma be able to do quality science because of it. So I look forward to working with folks who are on the Roman committee to really think about how we engage folks at smaller and underserved institutions.

I think we have time for a couple more questions on this very important topic. "Isn't there a need to start the process at an early career stage? In other words, targeting undergraduate -- when these guys are ready to go to grad school.

I think that is a great question and certainly a great point. I have been looking at and involved in pipeline issues for a long time, not just even at the undergraduate level, but even before that. What concerns me we are not making that much headway. I think we need to do both things, but we definitely need to move from just thinking about pipeline issues to thinking about retention. Because we are definitely not doing a good job entertaining even the people who do come up through our undergraduate institutions and getting them into graduate school and getting them into a career positions. Yes, we absolutely have to do both. I am concerned that we had not been putting enough emphasis and enough resources into how we are doing retention and how we are building collaborations, how we are making these people feel that they are part of the community.

I guess one more question. What role do you see in our lab and Roman data sets analysis resources planning and building science experience and expertise at non-European and U.S. centric institutions especially in countries and universities where current expertise is not in telescope data science. This is a question.

I guess this is an international question. Certainly, making data available in the ways that we are talking about will help people across the community internationally and nationally in the U.S. I think that as we have opportunities to do training, and we think about the ways in which we want to do training, you know, doing training on platforms and tools for students the way we do it for students is not necessarily the way that later career folks might want to engage with those data sets because maybe they don't have as much dedicated time. Thinking about, what are the ways that we do -- that we make knowledge available, that we make training available, that we make expertise available in addition to how we make data available will not just help us nationally, it can help us internationally. And if we have to worry on top about language barriers and other issues, and I think we move on from there. let's try and get some funding and resources for doing sort of the groundwork first.

Okay. People are enjoying -- they are certainly engaged with your talk. One question I want to ask you and leave you with one final question from Rebecca who says "I have a feeling that the move to online conferences may have made them more inclusive. do conference organizers or others have data on inclusivity? That's a question and a comment, I guess.

I think it's an interesting thing. In some ways, it's making things more inclusive at least four getting started maybe in collaborating with folks. But like the person said, you know, actually becoming understanding, getting to know somebody, really building a network and a collaboration requires more than just, you know, and a zoom connection and other things. You really have to start working with folks. I think there are pluses and minuses. I would caution again when we look at policies for setting things up and how we are going to do things that we try something out and adjusted if we are not getting the results we want. I can also see many barriers to this kind of interaction that are just different barriers and different biases than we had when things were in person. Again, we need a mix. We need to also step back and reassess at every opportunity.

Okay. I think I'm then I go ahead and ask one final question. I think this is an interesting one. The question has to do with the dual anonymous practice. Supportive of it as a way of reducing bias, but has been wondering if it reflects equality more than equity. The question is, other ways to ensure an equity is achieved when the proposal, abstracts, et cetera are anonymously reviewed?

Yes. This is my concern. This is exactly my concern about dual anonymous. I don't have a problem with dual anonymous. I think it's great to have things anonymous in a first stage. However, I do think that we are not achieving equity when we fully and wholly anonymized things. There are differences in opportunities for folks who have access to telescopes, access to the ability to do their initial research. We really need to take into account at some stage in the process who folks are and what they need. Because I think if we don't do that, we are not addressing equity. We might be addressing equality. But we are not starting on a level playing field. My concern is that we don't keep things in place that just assume that everybody starts on a level playing field, because they don't.

Okay. Well, there are many more questions than we actually have time for. With the other speakers, I strongly encourage you to read the questions on your channel, which is diversity, equity, and inclusion, and answer them and look at some of the discussions. I want to thank all of our speakers today starting with -- for a very interesting morning an introduction to our conference. And I think we now break until 12:30 Eastern daylight Time. Again, if you have additional questions for any of the speakers or discussion, please use the slack channels. Again, thank you to all of our speakers. I will clap. [Applause] So, I guess we are now on break until 12:30.

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